

POLITICAL SCIENCES

RETHINKING POLITICAL REPRESENTATION IN LATIN AMERICA: VOICES OF CITIZENS IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

This work is research on political representation in Latin America: A critical analysis from an academic perspective where we address a central issue for the region: the relationship between citizens and their political representatives, with which, as a consequence, the figure of "Political Caste" emerges." In this context we aim to understand the challenges and opportunities faced by Latin American democracies and identify the factors that influence political representation. As first findings: there is a significant gap between representation and the needs of citizens. This gap is manifested in various indicators, such as low trust in political institutions, high electoral abstention and the perception that representatives do not respond to the interests of the population. The analysis and treatment given to the information has been strictly qualitative. Conclusions: Research on political representation in Latin America is crucial to understanding the challenges and opportunities faced by democracies in the region. Research findings can inform public policy design, institutional reform, and the promotion of citizen participation. It is essential to continue researching in this field to move towards more just and inclusive democracies in Latin America.

Keywords: Latin America, politics, citizenship, political caste.

Introduction

"...Argentine politics was once again dominated, as so many times in the past, by disagreement. The factional struggle, in which each of the parties assumed that it could only win at the expense of the others, seemed to prevail. But, as usual, these conflicts were fueled both by programmatic differences and irreconcilable interests and by the long-cultivated propensity to privilege short-term interests and distrust the advantages of cooperation, even between political and sectoral leaders who in reality did not differ. both with each other..."¹

Marcos Navaro².

The 21st century in Latin America has been marked by growing citizen discontent with the political class, which has given rise to its name as a "caste." This unrest has manifested itself in various ways, from the emergence of social movements and protests to support for populist and authoritarian leaders. The roots of citizen unrest are deep and complex, among the main causes we find: disconnection between the political class and the population, widespread corruption in the region has undermined trust in institutions and has generated a feeling of injustice and frustration, inequality. It is another aspect that afflicts society; in addition, some governments in the region are perceived as ineffective and incapable of solving fundamental problems such as poverty, insecurity and lack of access to basic services.

As for the term "political caste," it is used to describe a group of people who hold political power in an exclusive and hereditary manner, without responding to the needs and interests of the population. Raffaele Maria de los Angeles (2023) in his article mentions that "...The political analyst and former president of the Latin American Association of Political Consultants (ALaCoP), Carlos Fara, maintains that the caste for Milei is "the political establishment and, above all, the two great political coalitions: Unión por la Patria and the one represented by Patricia Bullrich, "Together for Change...". In response to citizen unrest, a new civic activism has emerged that challenges the inertia of traditional politicians. "... At the same time, the process of change that is taking place in this century around the expansion of citizenship, is projected to new dimensions of social positioning, which recognizes its starting point in social rights and advances towards the consolidation of new rights that they operate in a complementary way to guarantee a status of citizen according to the demands of the time..." Pérez Gamón C. M. (2023).

Citizen unrest with the political class in Latin America is a complex phenomenon that requires comprehensive solutions. Among the main challenges we find: Citizen unrest in Latin America is a sign that the region needs profound change. Governments in the region must address the underlying problems that fuel this unrest and take measures to build more just, equitable and democratic societies. The new civic activism has a fundamental role to play in this transformation

¹ Navaro, M. (2021) *Historia de la Argentina 1955-2020. Siglo veintiuno*. Buenos Aires. Argentina, p. 314.

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process in the 21st century. The analysis and treatment given to the information in this research has been strictly qualitative.

Investigation

Disconnection of the Political Class in Latin America.

Latin America, a region rich in natural and cultural resources, faces a constant paradox: the potential for its development is held back by a political class that often seems disconnected from the needs of its population. This disconnection manifests itself in multiple forms, from the lack of effective public policies to widespread corruption.

In recent years, Brazil has witnessed a series of corruption scandals involving senior government officials and state-owned companies. The Lava Jato case, one of the largest corruption scandals in the history of Latin America, revealed a bribery scheme that affected numerous politicians and businessmen. According to Gerardo L. (2021), "...In Portuguese, Lava Jato means "car wash" and refers to the place where the case began: a gas station in Brasilia where no one cleaned cars, but the police suspected they were laundering money. By investigating and using plea agreements with defendants, prosecutors discovered a bribery scheme for multimillion-dollar contracts by the state oil company Petrobras with construction companies in Brazil..." This scandal not only exposed systemic corruption, but also showed how the political class was more focused on its own interests than on those of the population.

However, Lula was once again a candidate for President of Brazil Perez Gamón C. M. (2023) "...In the 2022 elections, after surpassing Jair Bolsonaro, it is the return of the left to power, thus culminating the most right-wing government in decades, amid ideological antagonisms that divided Brazilian citizens. Meanwhile, disgruntled Bolsonaro supporters blocked highways and camped out in front of barracks to protest the results as the defeated president marched on Florida. While Lula gave a speech in which he guaranteed the citizenry that..." the wheels of our economy will start

rolling again, promoting job creation, wage increases and debt renegotiation for those families that have been losing acquisitive power..."

Meanwhile, the humanitarian and economic crisis in Venezuela is another clear example of this disconnection. Despite being one of the countries with the largest oil reserves in the world, its population suffers from food and medicine shortages, hyperinflation, and massive emigration. According to the newspaper Clarín (2021) "...From the presidential palace, President Nicolás Maduro periodically takes over radio and TV broadcasts to deliver speeches that aim to project stability in the face of a country that is falling apart. But as the Venezuelan state disintegrates under the weight of Maduro's corrupt leadership and U.S. sanctions, his government is losing control of segments of the country, even within its stronghold: the capital, Caracas...", the government's policies Venezuelans, especially under the leadership of Nicolás Maduro, have prioritized the consolidation of political power over the basic needs of citizens.

Regarding the terms Political Caste, Claudio Fernández (2023,40-41) adds "... it became vital for Milei's political discourse, to the detriment of other terms such as "oligarchy", "political corporation", or "politicians"...". The term political caste synthesizes in one term the criticism of politicians, the centerpiece of his platform for the elections. The term political caste

³ América Latina son los países que hablan lenguas romances que descienden del latín. América Latina se compone de 33 países. Brasil es el país más grande y poblado de América

Latina. Recuperado de <http://bigkarta.ru/es/mapa-america-latina.htm>

not only excludes, but highlights in Milei's political discourse, the most relevant aspect: that of the privileges of politicians. The term "caste" refers directly to that sense. It is not only criticism of politicians, but also of the privileges of politicians, who are characterized as a

strongly established social group. The political caste symbolizes a social group in which social stratification and the impossibility of ascending or descending in the social stratum does not exist."

Javier Milei- Argentina Luis I. Lula da Silva- Brasil⁴.

First Findings.

Impact of Political Disconnection

The disconnection between the political class and citizens has several negative consequences. First of all, it generates distrust in democratic institutions. When citizens perceive that their leaders are not interested in their needs, electoral participation and civic engagement decrease. This can lead to the strengthening of populist movements that promise quick and often authoritarian solutions.

Citizen participation is essential to strengthen political representation. An active and informed citizenry can demand accountability from its representatives, influence the political agenda and promote public policies that respond to their needs.

Conclusions

The concept of "political caste" is a criticism that emphasizes the privileges of politicians, characterizing them as a rigid and established social group, without social mobility. This term not only excludes politicians, but also highlights the disconnection between them and the needs of the population. In Latin America, this disconnection is a persistent problem that requires urgent attention.

To move towards sustainable and equitable development, it is essential that political leaders commit to transparency, accountability and the implementation of public policies that respond to the real needs of citizens. Without this commitment, the region will continue to be limited by lack of trust and government inefficiency.

Research on political representation in Latin America is crucial to understanding the challenges and opportunities facing democracies in the region. Research findings can inform public policy design, institutional reform, and the promotion of citizen participation.

Furthermore, for future research, it would be relevant to analyze in depth the behavior of youth on social

networks, since this group has a crucial role in shaping the political and social future of the region.

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⁴ Pignotti D. (2023) *Lula y Milei, dos caminos opuestos para gobernar.* Página 12. Recuperado de <https://www.pagina12.com.ar/698160-lula-y-milei-dos-caminos-opuestos-para-gobernar>

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